

IN VITRO CULTURE ESTABLISHMENT AND PROLIFERATION OF BELARUSSIAN APPLE CULTIVARS

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Abstract. *The collection of fruit, berry, nut and grapes of Institute for Fruit Growing of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus was declared a National Treasure and included in the State Register of Scientific Objects (No. 6) in 2012. This plant genebank has no analogues in Belarus. The collection resources are kept alive, 3-6 plants of each cultivar or hybrid, in field conditions (in situ) on the area of 20 ha (ag. Samokhvalovichy, Minsk district). On January 1, 2024 the collection amounted to 5579 accessions, of which 1469 were apple accessions.*

In the Department of Biotechnology "Institute for Fruit Growing" of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus a duplicate active collection, preserved in sterile conditions at the temperature of +23...25°C was established in January, 2019. On October 1, 2024, the in vitro collection included 2 cultivars of Malus Mill.: mandate cultivars of belarussian breeding "Zoya"[®] and "Zorka".

The objective of the present research: to develop the protocol for in vitro establishment of apple cultivars of Belarussian breeding for getting sterile explants for including and maintaining apple germplasm in in vitro collection.

8.2% of sterile and viable explants for cv. Zoya[®] and 6.5% for cv. Zorka were recorded in the developed protocol for in vitro establishment. This number of sterile explants provides the necessary number of apple regenerants to maintain the in vitro genebank.

The highest multiplication rate (4.8) and the average number of microcuttings with a height of 1.4-2 cm (5.2 pieces) was obtained on the modified MS with nystatin after 5 weeks of subcultivation.

Using cv. Zorka as a model cultivar, it was found that on the modified DKW medium containing Fe-EDTA, 1.4 times more regenerants were formed in the conglomerate than on the medium containing Fe-EDDHA.

Long-term cultivation (8 weeks) on modified DKW medium is also possible, and the multiplication rate was 1.3 times higher than after 7 weeks of subcultivation.

Keywords: *in vitro establishment of apple cultivars, Belarussian apple cultivars, micropropagation of apple.*

Introduction

The collection of fruit, berry, nut and grapes of Institute for Fruit Growing of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus was declared a National Treasure and included in the State Register of Scientific Objects (No. 6) in 2012. This plant genebank has no analogues in Belarus. The collection resources are kept alive, 3-6 plants of each cultivar or hybrid, in field conditions (*in situ*) on the area of 20 ha (ag. Samokhvalovichy, Minsk district). On October 1, 2024 the collection amounted to 5579 accessions, of which 1469 were apple accessions.

The main prerequisite for the *ex situ* conservation establishment of plantations, and the improvement, is production of a large number of plants of mandate apple cultivars.

In the Department of Biotechnology "Institute for Fruit Growing" a duplicate active collection, preserved in sterile conditions at the temperature of +23...25°C was established. The results of this work made it possible to include apple germplasm cv. Zoya® and Zorka in the *in vitro* collection. On October 1, 2024, the *in vitro* collection included 2 cultivars of *Malus* Mill. (cv. Zoya® and Zorka) with 10 plants each.

The success of the initiation stage of apple micropropagation depends on different parameters (genotypes, age of mother plant, season for collection of explants, source of explants (shoot tips in dormant or actively growing buds, etc.), the sterilisation method, the *in vitro* physical and chemical conditions, etc.) [1]. All these parameters should help to solve basic problems: high-level contamination of collected explants and phenol-induced browning of explants.

The objective of the present research: to develop the protocol for *in vitro* establishment of apple cultivars of Belarussian breeding for getting sterile explants for including and maintaining apple germplasm in *in vitro* collection.

Material and methods

The objects of research – mandate apple cultivars of Belarussian breeding "Zoya"® and "Zorka". The term of *in vitro* culture establishment is the period of winter-dormancy of mother plants. Sources of explants – one-year woody cuttings from field-grown free of viruses mother plants (Apple chlorotic leaf spot virus (ACLSV), Apple mosaic virus (ApMV), Apple stem-grooving virus (ASGV)).

***In vitro* establishment.** Cuttings were placed in a glass jar with water and left at room temperature until 1-1.5 cm buds germinated. Explants for establishment - germinated buds of 1-1.5 cm.

Three sterilisation schemes were researched: non-sterile conditions: running tap water washed with lye, fungicide solution with 2 drops of Tween-20 for 1 hour (750 mg Antracol® with 300 ml distilled water), running tap water washed for 10 min; sterile conditions: 70% ethanol for 1 min, 0.1% mercuric chloride (HgCl₂) for 4; 5; 20 min, sterile solution CaCl₂ (2.5 g/l) for 5 min, washed three times with sterile distilled water for 5 min each.

The variations of the culture media used in the introduction step are in Table 1.

Table1 – Nutrition mediums for establishment of apple explants

Nutrition medium		Mineral compound	Growth regulators	Agar-agar	Additional medium compounds
Medium 1	Solidified medium	Modified medium Murashige-Skoog (MS)	1 mg/L 6-BA 0,3 mg/L IBA	+	60 mg/L PVP 4 tablets Nystatin/L
Medium 2	Liquid medium		0,2 mg/L GA ₃	-	

pH of the medium - 5.76-5.77 before the addition of nystatin tablets and agar-agar to the nutrient medium.

Transplantation of explants into fresh nutrient medium to avoid the negative effect of phenolic browning was carried out on the 3rd and 7th day of cultivation. Romadanova N.V. recommended daily transplantation of apple explants into fresh medium to avoid necrosis [2].

The efficiency of obtaining sterile and actively regenerating explants was analysed after 4 weeks. Parameters of efficiency of the introduction stage of apple explants: infected explants, %; necrotised explants, %; sterile viable explants, %; explants with phenolic compounds, %.

Multiplication stage. The development of regenerants at the micropropagation stage was evaluated on nutrient media, the variants of which are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2 - Nutrition mediums for the micropropagation stage

Nutrition medium	Mineral compound	Growth regulators	Additional medium compounds
MS	Modified medium MS	1 mg/L 6-BA 0.01 mg/L IBA	non
DKW	Modified medium DKW	0.2 mg/L GA ₃	
MS/ Nystatin	Modified medium MS		4 tablets Nystatin/L (500 000 UI) (OJSC «Borisov Plant of Medical Preparations»)
DKW/ Nystatin	Modified medium DKW		

Subcultivation time – 5 weeks.

Table 3 – Nutrition mediums for shoot multiplication stage of cv. Zorka

Nutrition medium	Mineral compound	Growth regulators	Iron chelate formulas	Additional medium compounds
DKW	Modified medium DKW	1 mg/L 6-BA 0.01 mg/L IBA 0.2 mg/L GA ₃	DKW standard Fe-EDTA concentration	4 tablets Nystatin /L (500 000 UI) per liter
DKW/Fe			200 mg/L Fe-EDDHA (Duchefa Biochemie®)	

Subcultivation time – 8 weeks.

pH of the medium - 5,7-5,8 before the addition of nystatin tablets and agar-agar to the nutrient mediums.

Parameters of efficiency of the shoot multiplication stage: multiplication rate (average number of regenerants in the conglomerate); number of microcuttings/explant, psc.; shoot length, cm.

Cultivation conditions: illumination 2.5-3 thousand lux (OSRAM), temperature +23...+25°C, photoperiod 16/8 hours.

Statistical processing was carried out using Statistics 10.0 software. One- and two-factor analyses were carried out using ANOVA. Duncan's test was used to compare means.

Results of scientific work

***In vitro* establishment.** When analysing the results of *in vitro* establishment of apple varieties, a highly significant influence of the studied sterilisation schemes and nutrient media and their mutual influence on the parameters of regeneration activity of explants is noted (Table 4).

In general, the regenerative capacity of explants under the selected conditions was very low: from 6.5 to 8.2%. The main reasons for this result: active synthesis of phenolic compounds by the explants and their high infection associated with morphological features of the plants (pubescence of leaf rudiments in the bud and leaves themselves). It should be noted that the infection, which was not observed at the establishment stage, appears at the next stage of micropropagation.

The use of sterilisation with 0.1% HgCl₂ for 20 minutes resulted in a high rate of necrosis (100%).

The use of liquid nutrient medium favoured the production of sterile viable explants. The number of explants with phenolic compounds was higher in the agar medium (26.7%) than in the medium without agar (16.7%) (see Table 4).

Table 4 – Effect of nutrient media and exposure to 0.1% HgCl₂ on the efficiency of the *in vitro* culture establishment of apple cultivars

Cultivar	Sterilization scheme (Factor A)	Nutrition medium (Factor B)	Infected explants, %	Necrosis explants, %	Explants with phenolic compounds, %	Sterile and viable, explants %
			p<0,001	p<0,001	p<0,001	p<0,001
Zoya®	4 minutes	Medium 1	22,3	54,6	23,1	0
		Medium 2	21,5	58,9	11,4	8,2
	5minutes	Medium 1	13,1	50,2	36,4	0
		Medium 2	12,0	65,6	22,4	0
	20 minutes	Medium 1	0	100	0	0
		Medium 2	0	100	0	0
Zorka	4 minutes	Medium 1	13,5	41,3	45,2	0
		Medium 2	20,1	50,3	23,1	6,5
	5minutes	Medium 1	15,6	29,2	55,2	0
		Medium 2	21,4	35,5	43,1	0
	20 minutes	Medium 1	0	100	0	0
		Medium 2	0	100	0	0
Sterilization scheme (Factor A)			p<0,01	p<0,001	p<0,001	p<0,001
4 minutes			19,4a*	51,3b	25,7b	3,7a
5minutes			15,5b	45,1c	39,3a	0b
20 minutes			0	100a	0	0
Nutrition medium (Factor B)			p<0,01	p<0,15	p<0,001	p<0,001
Medium 1			10,8b	62,6	26,7a	0b
Medium 2			12,5a	68,4	16,7b	2,5a

Means followed by the same letter within the same column are not significantly different (P=0.05) using Duncan’s multiple range test.

Multiplication stage. Statistical processing of the results obtained allows us to note that all the factors studied have a reliable effect on the multiplication rate of cv. Zoya® (Table 5). The presence of nystatin, added to the medium to prevent the development of bacterial infection, contributed to the inhibition of shoot multiplication: the multiplication rate on the medium with nystatin was 3.4, which is lower than on the medium without nystatin (3.8). On the modified MS medium, this index was 1.5 times higher than on the modified DKW medium.

Table 5 – Development of regenerants cv. Zoya® at the multiplication stage for 5 weeks

Nystatin (Factor A)	Nutrition medium (Factor B)	Multiplication rate	Number of microcuttings/explant
		p<0,01	p<0,001
Free of Nystatin	MS	3,8b	4,2c
	DKW	3,8b	4,7b
Nystatin	MS/Nystatin	4,8a	5,2a
	DKW/Nystatin	2,1c	2,8d
Nystatin (Factor A)		p<0,001	p<0,001
Free of Nystatin		3,8a	4,4a
Nystatin		3,4b	4,0b
Nutrition medium (Factor B)		p<0,001	p<0,001
MS		4,3a	4,7a
DKW		2,9b	3,7b

In order to obtain the maximum multiplication rate, it is advisable to use MS with nystatin for the 5-week cultivation of regenerants, where the multiplication rate was 4.8 and, when microcutting regenerants, we obtained an average of 5.2 pieces of microcuttings with a length of 1.4-2 cm (see Table 5).

On the example of cv. Zorka, a reliable influence of iron forms on the multiplication rate was observed: on the DKW medium containing with Fe-EDTA, 1.4 times more regenerants are formed in conglomerate than on the medium with Fe-EDDHA (Table 6).

Table 6 - Effect of iron chelate type on the development of regenerants cv. Zorka at the micropropagation stage

Iron chelate formulas	Multiplication rate	Number of microcuttings/explant	Shoot length, cm
	p<0,001	p<0,001	p<0,5
DKW (Fe-EDDHA)	2,4b	3,5b	2,7
DKW (Fe-EDTA)	3,3a	4,7a	2,5

No significant effect of iron forms on growth processes was observed.

After 8 weeks of subcultivation, the multiplication rate was 1.3 times higher than after 7 weeks of cultivation (Table 7). For microcuttings, the number of cuttings obtained after 8 weeks of cultivation was also correspondingly higher than after 7 weeks of subcultivation.

Table 7 - Effect of cultivation time on the development of cv. Zorka on modified DKW medium with Nystatin (8 weeks)

Cultivation time	Multiplication rate	Number of microcuttings/explant
	p<0,001	p<0,001
7 weeks	1,8b	2,3b
8 weeks	2,3a	2,8a

Conclusions

In the course of the research, the most optimal conditions for the *in vitro* culture of explants of the Belarusian apple varieties Zoya[®] and Zorka were determined, which are reflected in the protocol.

Preparing of apple explants

1. The one-year old woody shoots at the winter-dormancy period;
2. Explant type: dormant buds, for which the cuttings are placed in a glass jar with water and left at room temperature until 1-1.5 cm buds germinate;

Sterilisation scheme of explants:

Under non-sterile conditions

1. Wash under tap water with washing soap;
2. Solution of fungicide for 1 hour (750 mg Anthracol[®] per 300 ml distilled water with 2 drops of Tween 20);
3. Rinse under tap water for 10 min.

Under sterile conditions

1. 70% ethyl alcohol for 1 min;
2. 0.1% HgCl₂ for 4 min;
3. CaCl₂ (2.5 g/L) sterile solution for 5 min;
4. Three rinses with sterile distilled water for 5 min each.

Nutrition medium for *in vitro* establishment: modified Murashige and Skoog (MS) liquid nutrient medium supplemented with polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) - 60 mg/L; 6-BA - 1 mg/L, IBA - 0.3 mg/L and GA₃ - 0.2 mg/L as phytohormones.

Frequent transplanting of explants into fresh medium is recommended to eliminate the negative effects of phenolic products (on day 3 and day 7 of cultivation).

In vitro cultivation conditions: illumination 2.5-3 thousand lux, temperature +23...+25°C, photoperiod 16/8 hours. The cultivation time is 4 weeks.

8.2% of sterile and viable explants for cv. Zoya[®] and 6.5% for cv. Zorka were recorded in the developed protocol for *in vitro* establishment. This number of sterile explants provides the necessary number of apple regenerants to maintain the *in vitro* genebank.

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Long-term cultivation (8 weeks) on modified DKW medium is also possible, and the multiplication rate was 1.3 times higher than after 7 weeks of subcultivation.

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